

[v1 - August 12, 2024]

Development of Type Token is ongoing and further releases will be announced on the site: <https://humanfactorsinsemantics.net>

Type Token

a Foundational Ontology Game

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Summary

Type Token is a card game developed by Max Willis and Greta Adamo to learn and explore foundational ontological principles in a fun and intuitive collaborative modeling format. The game consists of 50+ cards, each of which is printed with either a photograph - representing a *token*, instance or individual - or a text which can be arranged to articulate classes, i.e. *types*, and hierarchies of classes. Rule-based interactions facilitate players to create a multidirectional model on the playing field, and gameplay to discuss meanings and their interpretations in a process of ontology-based discourse.

Type Token cards arrangement.

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The game

Version One (v1) of the Type Token Game consists of two decks. **Deck A** contains photographs of dogs, dog art, and dog-related Egyptian relics, and abstract classification constructs such as "Category", "Kind", "Subkind", with more specialized types such as "Dog", "Chihuahua", "Bernese Mountain Dog", as well as "Art", "Painting", "Print" and "Sculpture".

Deck B contains photographs of cats, cat art, Egyptian cat relics (among others) with additional abstract constructs including "Phase", "Role", and "Collective" as well as specialized types such as "Cat", "Mother cat", "Egyptian Cat", and "Cat mummy".

The two decks can be played separately, for example **Deck A** first to introduce gameplay, or can be mixed together to generate more evolved discourse and ontological possibilities in the gameplay.

Two examples of Type Token in action.

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The rules

The rules of Type Token game are as follows:

- Three to 10 players are each dealt 7 cards from the deck;
- The remaining cards are placed face-down on the playing field and the top card is revealed, thus starting the collaborative model;
- Taking turns, each player draws one card from the deck, and proceeds to add as many cards as they can to the collaborative ontological model;
- The first player to place all of their cards wins the round;
- Cards are reshuffled, and play begins anew.

*Cards placed by players must utilize at least one card from the existing model.

*Cards must form coherent ontological structure in line with the ontological commitments of the game.

*Other players can dispute a player's arrangements, at which point the player must defend their play position, or retrieve their cards and lose their turn.

*Cards can be placed in any direction: horizontal, vertical or otherwise.

Additional Type Token rule cards (contained in **Deck B**) facilitate adversarial play, and allow for the game, or players to overcome stasis.

Some background and future developments

Type Token is one of a series of artifacts and interventions developed around ideas of ontology-based participatory sensemaking [1] in which the authors explore game and play modalities and social learning. Ontologies and their applications are explored towards aligning participant mental models, through discussion and dialogue in group workshops. Type Token is based on the ontological commitments of the *Unified Foundational Ontology* (UFO) [2] and the ontology-driven conceptual modeling language ontoUML [3].¹ Type Token is the first module in a multi-ontology game project that addresses ontological positions from UFO and other foundational ontologies, such as *Basic Formal Ontology* (BFO) [4] and *Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering* (DOLCE) [5].

¹ <https://ontouml.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

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